

A New Domain Knowledge-Driven Approach to Single Molecule Track Analysis in Live Bacteria

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Accepted for oral presentation at the **91st Harden Conference: Single Molecule Bacteriology III**

Organised by the Biochemical Society

30 September – 3 October 2024

De Vere Cotswold Water Park, Gloucestershire, United Kingdom

Session eleven – Single-molecule methods II – Default Location, 03/10/2024, 10:45 – 12:15

Scheduled presentation: **3 October 2024, 12:00–12:15**

Abstract ID: **OC015**

Abstract

Single molecule tracking in live bacteria has dramatically increased observation times due to more stable probes, improved labelling strategies, and time-lapse imaging. These advancements extend observation times from milliseconds to minutes, capturing entire biological processes from the perspective of a single molecule. At the Single Molecule Bacteriology II meeting in 2022, the first applications of this technique were demonstrated in various bacterial processes.

There exists a major remaining challenge in analysing these extended tracks to extract the sequential information that is now available. Existing pipelines, designed for datasets with 10,000-100,000 short tracks, use hidden Markov models and diffusion analysis to build an ensemble picture from brief snapshots, rather than analysing tracks individually in their full temporal context.

We present a new approach to single molecule tracking analysis in live bacteria, using machine learning and domain knowledge to obtain whole-process information from these more complex tracks. Our approach applies recurrent neural networks for time series segmentation of long-lived single molecule tracks, integrating spatial information and avoiding hardcoded rules and assumptions from diffusion or statistical models.

Using real experimental data of DNA binding proteins, and simulations, we demonstrate how this method extracts new insights from long-duration single molecule tracking experiments in vivo. Our publicly available software, driven by a bespoke GUI, integrates seamlessly into major single molecule tracking pipelines. We will discuss this new approach and its applications.